

D8.7 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v2

WP8 - Dissemination, sustainability and exploitation

Version: 1.00

SPHINX

A Universal Cyber Security Toolkit for
Health-Care Industry

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Document information

Grant Agreement Number	826183		Acronym	SPHINX	
Full Title	A Universal Cyber Security Toolkit for Health-Care Industry				
Topic	SU-TDS-02-2018 Toolkit for assessing and reducing cyber risks in hospitals and care centres to protect privacy/data/infrastructures				
Funding scheme	RIA - Research and Innovation action				
Start Date	1 st January 2019	Duration	36 months		
Project URL	http://sphinx-project.eu/				
EU Project Officer	Reza RAZAVI (CNECT/H/03)				
Project Coordinator	Dimitris Askounis, National Technical University of Athens - NTUA				
Deliverable	D8.7. Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v2				
Work Package	WP8 – Dissemination, sustainability and exploitation				
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M24	Actual	M24	
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	P - Public		
Lead Beneficiary	VILABS				
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Keywords	Sustainability, cybersecurity, e-health				

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.10	20/10/2020	Draft	ToC preparation	Ilias Trochidis & Vasileios Voulgarakis (ViLabs)
0.11	02/11/2020	Draft	Agreement on TOC and Partners' assignments	All partners
0.20	2/11/2020	Draft	Deliverable preparation	Ilias Trochidis & Vasileios Voulgarakis (ViLabs)
0.30	7/12/2020	Draft	First full draft	Ilias Trochidis & Vasileios Voulgarakis (ViLabs)
0.40	11/12/2020	Draft	Pre-final draft sent for review	Ilias Trochidis & Vasileios Voulgarakis (ViLabs)
0.50	17/11/2020	Draft	Minor comments and updates	Fotios Gioulekas, Athanasios Tzikas, Evangelos Stamatiadis, Konstantinos Gounaris (DYPE5), Sergiu Marin (Poliaris Medical), Ilias Lamprinos (ICOM)
0.60	18/11/2020	Draft	Deliverable update to reflect comments	Ilias Trochidis & Vasileios Voulgarakis (ViLabs)
0.70	22/12/2020	Pre-final	Quality Control	George Doukas (NTUA)
1.00	23/12/2020	Final	Final	Christos Ntanos (NTUA)

Executive Summary

This is the second version of the SPHINX “Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans” document. The first version “D8.4. Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v1” that was submitted by the end of year 1 of the project (M12 – December 2019) briefly presented the SPHINX project outcomes, the overall exploitation plan that the entire consortium should follow and the KPIs that should be reached by the end of this project.

This version is an updated version and describes more clearly the SPHINX exploitable outcomes since we are on month 24 of the project with all the components having their first version developed. Overall, SPHINX will produce five (5) exploitation outcomes including:

- the SPHINX toolkit that is the main technical outcome of the project,
- the SPHINX individual components that the SPHINX toolkit is composed of,
- the pilot cases success stories,
- the policy recommendations and best practices from the implementation of SPHINX platform in replicated real environments, and
- the scientific knowledge that will be generated through the R&D activities.

The outcomes will be exploited interdisciplinary group formed by the different partner organisations, in IT Industry, Health Provision Organisations (end users), and Academia. Due to their different nature, each organisation will exploit various outcomes. To do so, SPHINX will develop three basic exploitation options; i) the business cases for the platform and its components, ii) the replication plan to support Health Provision Organisations to deploy the SPHINX platform and iii) the concrete exploitation plans to secure the continuation of the scientific knowledge produced, after the end of the project. These exploitation options will be presented to the targeted audience in order to receive their feedback and engage them in the project activities. Different target audience groups (Industry, Health Provision Organisations, Research, Related EU funded projects, and Policy makers) will be engaged to exploit different outcomes.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

This report is the second version of the **SPHINX Exploitation, Sustainability and Business Plan** and incorporates all actions involved in setting up the environment for commercialising the SPHINX toolkit and for further exploiting the SPHINX outcomes. The report is the main outcome of “Task 8.3: Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans”. At the end of the project (M36) the third and final version of the exploitation and sustainability plan will be delivered.

In this context, this report aims to:

- Present the key SPHINX exploitable results focusing on the exploitation goals for each outcome.
- Outline the overall project exploitation plan justifying the goals and corresponding targets set until the end of the project.
- Identify the business cases for exploitation.
- Define the sustainability plan that the consortium will follow to sustain the project outcomes, beyond the end of the project.
- Define the plan to identify the individual exploitation plans that different partners (industry, SMES, public authorities, universities etc.) will implement to sustain the project outcomes after the contractual end.

The forthcoming period the key outcome of the project, the SPHINX toolkit and its individual components will be deployed in pilot conditions. Therefore, the final version of this report (M36) will focus on the identification and validation of the SPHINX value proposition and the development of the SPHINX business models and business plan to stimulate the commercialisation prospects of the SPHINX toolkit. In parallel, there are a number of exploitation activities that are foreseen that will assist the wide exploitation and sustainability of the SPHINX outcomes.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The document begins with a presentation of the SPHINX main exploitable outcomes (Section 2) and provides a summary of the exploitation goals for these outcomes (3). The document continues with an analysis of the plan for identifying the SPHINX business models and for presenting the SPHINX business plan (Section 4) while the plan for sustaining the results of the project is presented in Section 5. Initial individual exploitation plans have already been presented in the previous version of this deliverable and this document presents the exploitation questionnaire that will be distributed to partners for gathering feedback with regards to their individual exploitation plans (Section 6). Finally, the document concludes with a summary of all the Exploitation activities (Section 7) that will be carried out during the final year of the project in order to make sure that all the project outcomes will be disseminated and exploited appropriately to the right target audience.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This report is the outcome of “Task 8.3: Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans”, which is a horizontal action across all SPHINX Work Packages. In particular, within WP8 Dissemination, sustainability and exploitation, all tasks are complementary. It is also closely connected with the different tasks related to IPRs (“Task 7.4 Legal analysis evaluation of the SPHINX use cases and business model”, “Task 8.5 Knowledge Management and IPR Protection”). Besides, this task aligns with the WPs (WP2,3,4,5,6) which are related to the identification of requirements and architecture and the development of the SPHINX components and toolkit and therefore, the exploitation plan should be updated according to the developed project results. Finally, Task 8.3 is also aligned to “WP7 Technology Validation Pilots and Privacy assessment”, because it is focusing on the

implementation of SPHINX toolkit in replicated/emulated settings of real environments which impacts the exploitation of the results. In that respect, the exploitation needs to have an overall understanding of the different work that is being implemented in all SPHINX work packages and tasks.

2 SPHINX exploitable outcomes

In this section we describe in detail the SPHINX key exploitable outcomes that this exploitation and sustainability plan is focused on. The exploitable outcomes have been identified in the previous version of this deliverable and a more detailed presentation of these outcomes is provided here. The key exploitable outcomes of SPHINX project are the following (Figure 1):

- SPHINX toolkit
- SPHINX individual components
- Pilot cases success stories and replication guidelines
- SPHINX policy recommendations and best practices
- Scientific and technical knowledge

Figure 1: SPHINX exploitable outcomes

The main exploitable outcome of the project is the **SPHINX toolkit**. For the SPHINX toolkit, the exploitation and sustainability plan will focus on identifying its sustainability and commercialization potential. For that reason, the plan for developing the final SPHINX business models and business plan will be described.

The SPHINX toolkit comprises of **individual components** that are interoperable and reusable, adhering to commonly accepted best practices of object-oriented software design flow. For these individual components, the exploitation and sustainability plan will focus on a) exploiting and sustaining the components and the knowledge generated even after the end of the project, and b) identifying which of these components have commercialization and sustainability potential, thus assisting the technical partners to develop their individual business models.

Strong demonstration (WP7) of the SPHINX platform will take place at four pilot sites (General Hospital of Volos (Greece), University Hospital of Larissa (Greece), Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (Portugal), and POLARIS Medical Clinic (Romania). These demonstrations will result to valuable knowledge, including; the **success stories** that will stem from the pilot implementations, the key **policy recommendations** at national and EU level, and the **replication guidelines** that external Health Delivery Organisations could follow to deploy the SPHINX platform.

Finally, several **scientific papers** with open access will be publicly available, allowing the maximum outreach and exploitation potential of the scientific and technical project knowledge. This action is mostly linked with “Task 8.1 Dissemination activities”.

2.1 The SPHINX toolkit

2.1.1 Description

SPHINX major exploitable technical outcome is the **SPHINX Universal Cyber Security Toolkit for the Health and Care Domain** that enhances the cyber protection of the healthcare IT ecosystem and ensures the patients’ data privacy and integrity. The SPHINX toolkit offers an embedded, smart and robust security awareness layer, able to identify modern and advanced cyber threats, enhanced with a personalised data security management tool.

The SPHINX architecture (Figure 2) has the capability to concentrate and handle the data of many devices or services, thus covering a wide range of use case scenarios. The SPHINX users are kept informed at any time via highly comprehensive live dashboards and visual analytics, while being able to interact with the services and functions of the proposed solution in an intuitive and user-friendly way.

Figure 2: SPHINX architecture

The SPHINX automated zero-touch device and service verification toolkit is easily adapted or embedded to existing, medical, clinical or health available infrastructures, while a user may choose from a number of available security services through the SPHINX cyber security toolbox.

SPHINX further embeds an innovative architecture to fulfil the following purposes: (a) scrutable user-side personalisation with dynamic privacy control by exploiting a predefined configuration (b) re-usability of the parts of a user model across different services.

The usability of the SPHINX Platform is paramount to the widespread uptake and usage of the project. It is designed to facilitate the operation of the SPHINX toolkit in real-life conditions allowing regular technology users (not limited to cyber security experts) to operate the system.

SPHINX cutting-edge technology is expected to:

- increase the level and the **effectiveness of automation** of existing cybersecurity services,
- enhance **system self-defence and countermeasure**,
- **open up the cybersecurity 'blackbox'** to the health network users and
- build a certified and **trust** through advanced usable transparency tools derived from health and care personnel.

SPHINX consists of individual components (presented in the Section 2.2) that are being designed and developed in WP3, WP4 and WP5. The integrated SPHINX toolkit is being delivered in WP6 in different iterations. The first iteration is on M24 (December 2020), while the second is being delivered on M30 (June 2021).

SPHINX toolkit is being tested and validated via the execution of four pilot activities in three pilot sites in Greece, Romania and Portugal. These activities take place in WP7 from M20 until the end of the project.

2.1.2 Exploitation goals

In the previous version of the exploitation plan that was submitted on M12 (D8.4 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v1), there were a number of KPIs that we set for the exploitation of SPHINX. Below we present

an updated summary of the main exploitation objectives for the SPHINX toolkit and the actions needed to fulfil these objectives. In Section 7, we summarize the action plan (including deadlines) for implementing all the exploitation objectives of SPHINX.

Within the project duration the objectives of the exploitation plan for the SPHINX toolkit are:

A/A	Exploitation goal	Actions needed
1.	Verify the business potential of the SPHINX toolkit.	<p>Develop the SPHINX business models and the SPHINX business plan.</p> <p>Receive feedback from the pilot demonstrations (WP7) with regards to the sustainability and exploitation potential of the platform.</p> <p>Establish an open dialogue with at least three companies working in the healthcare cybersecurity domain, present the business models and gather feedback.</p> <p>Disseminate the SPHINX toolkit and its value to a wide target audience.</p>

Table 1: Exploitation objectives for the SPHINX toolkit

2.2 SPHINX individual components

2.2.1 Description of the SPHINX components

The SPHINX toolkit has a modular architecture that is composed of five building blocks and **twenty key components** that are being developed by different technical partners.

The SPHINX main building blocks are:

- **Device Verification and Certification Module,**
- **Automated Cyber Security Risk Assessment Module,**
- **Cyber Security Toolkit Module,**
- **Decision Support System and Interactive Dashboard,**
- **Third-party APIs.**

These modules are then detailed into a set of twenty-one key components that are interoperable and reusable, adhering to commonly accepted best practices of object-oriented software design. In the table below we present the name of each component, the module that his component belongs to, the SPHINX deliverable that is responsible for implementing this component, the development status and the actions implemented so far in terms of Dissemination and Exploitation (content created).

	A/A	Outcome	Status	Deliverables	Content created
Automated Cyber Security Risk Assessment Module	1	Vulnerability Assessment as a Service (VAaaS) Led by HMU	First version ready on M18	D3.3 (M18), D3.9 (M30)	Blog Video
	2	Data Traffic Monitoring (DTM) Led by SIMAVI	First version ready on M20	D4.1 (M20), D4.7 (M32)	Blog Video
	3	Anomaly Detection (AD) Led by SIMAVI	First version ready on M20	D4.1 (M20), D4.7 (M32)	Blog Video
	4	Real-time Cyber Risk Assessment (RCRA) Led by NTUA	First version ready on M18	D3.1 (M18), D3.7 (M30)	Blog Video
	5	Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) Led by PDMFC	First version ready on M20	D4.5 (M20), D4.11 (M32)	Blog Video
	6	Artificial Intelligence (AI) Honeypot (HP) Let by FINT	First version ready on M20	D4.4 (M20), D4.10 (M32)	Video
	7	Machine Learning-empowered Intrusion Detection (MLID) Led by AiDEAS	First version ready on M18	D3.4 (M18), D3.10 (M30)	Blog Video
	8	Forensic Data Collection Engine (FDCE) Led by NTUA	First version ready on M18	D3.1 (M18), D3.7 (M30)	Video Blog
	9	Homomorphic Encryption (HE) Let by TEC	First version ready on M20	D4.6 (M20), D4.12 (M32)	Blog Video
	10	Anonymisation and Privacy (AP)			Video
	11	Blockchain Based Threats Registry (BBTR) Led by TECHNALIA	First version ready on M20	D4.3 (M20), M4.9 (M32)	Video Blog

	12	Knowledge Base (KB) Led by NTUA	First version ready on M22	D5.5 (M22), D5.10 (M34)	Video
	13	Service Manager (SM) Led by ICOM	Implemented on M16	D6.1 (M16)	Video
Decision Support System and Interactive Dashboard	14	Decision Support System (DSS) Led by KT	First version ready on M22	D5.1 (M22), D5.6 (M34)	Video
	15	Analytic Engine (AE) Led by KT	First version ready on M22	D5.1 (M22), D5.6 (M34)	Video
	16	Interactive Dashboards (ID) Led by SIMAVI	First version ready on M22	D5.2 (M22), D5.7 (M34)	Video
Device Verification and Certification Module	17	Attack and Behaviour Simulators (ABS) Led by NTUA	First version ready on M22	D5.3, D5.4 (M22), D5.7, D5.8 (M34)	Video
	18	Sandbox (Data Inspection Component) Led by PDMFC	First version ready on M20	D4.2 (M20), D4.8 (M32)	Blog Video
	19	Cyber Security Toolbox (CST) Led by HMU	First version ready on M22	D5.5 (M22), D5.10 (M34)	Video
	20	SPHINX Application Programming Interface for Third Parties (S-API) Led by EDGE	First version ready on M18	D3.6 (M18), D3.12 (M30)	Blog Video

Table 2: SPHINX individual components

2.2.2 Exploitation goals

All of the SPHINX key components are interoperable and reusable, that means that they can be used autonomously. In SPHINX there are both **sustainability** and **exploitation** objectives for each component.

With regards to the **sustainability**, the aim is to implement all the necessary actions to maximize the potential of the use and further extension of the components after the end of the project. With regards to the **exploitation**, the aim is to convince key actors to use these components. Exploitation is closely associated with the sustainability of the project after its conclusion, since exploitation activities should ensure that the results of the project are used by its target groups and possibly are transferred to other contexts (e.g. other sectors).

Within the project duration the objectives of the exploitation plan for the SPHINX components are:

A/A	Exploitation goal	Actions needed
1.	Wider adoption of the individual components	<p>Nine (9) partners responsible for developing individual components (FINT, ICOM, PDMFC, KT, SIMAVI, TECHNALIA, EDGE, AIDEAS, TEC) should include these components to their portfolio of services.</p> <p>Exploit the components to a wide target audience through dissemination activities (e.g. blog posts, videos, presentation of the key outcomes).</p> <p>Examine which of these components could have commercialisation potential and assess the possibility to support partners in developing business models for these components.</p>

Table 3: Exploitation objectives for the SPHINX components

2.3 SPHINX pilot success stories

2.3.1 Description of the pilot sites

Three pilot activities will be conducted involving the four pilot areas. The planned SPHINX pilots are:

Pilots	Pilot Sites	Application Scenarios
Pilot in Greece: Intra-Region Patient Data Transfer	DYPE5 GHV; DYPE5 UHL	Sharing and Exchange of Healthcare Information
Cross-Border Pilot between Greece and Romania: Cross-border Medical Data Exchange	POLARIS; DYPE5	Cross-border Healthcare Service Delivery
Pilot in Portugal: Securing Advanced Patient Care in Hospital and Homecare Environments	HESE	mHealth and Remote Patient Monitoring

Table 4: SPHINX pilot activities

Detailed description of the pilot activities is included in “D7.1 Pilot plans including WP7 evaluation framework” that was delivered on M18.

It is important that Exploitation activities are monitoring closely the pilot activities and record appropriately the deployment of the platform, the implementation of the different use cases and the success stories and lessons learnt. In parallel simple replication guidelines should be developed that will assist the exploitation of the SPHINX toolkit to other Health Delivery Organisations.

2.3.2 Exploitation goals

In terms of exploitation, the results of the pilot activities have been considered as an important outcome that should be exploited. It is important to implement all the necessary actions in order to maximize the potential of the sustainability of the SPHINX toolkit to the pilot sites and of the potential of installing the SPHINX toolkit to other Health Delivery Organisations.

Based on the above, the main exploitation goals of SPHINX pilot activities are the following:

A/A	Exploitation goal	Actions needed
1.	Maintain the pilot sites	Pilot partners will present the pilot demonstration and its impact on the persons who are responsible for local and/or national funding (e.g. ministries) or private investment companies. We envisage having at least 6 meetings (2 per pilot partner).
2.	Increase the potential to replicate the platform at external Health Delivery Organisations (HDO)	Develop replication plans. Present the results of the pilots and the replication plans to HDOs asking to express their interest and provide them with feedback to the replication plans. We expect that at least 3 Health Delivery Organisations (1 per pilot country) will express their interest.

Table 5: Exploitation objectives for the SPHINX pilots

2.4 Policy recommendations and best practices

2.4.1 Context

SPHINX research and development activities will result to key **policy recommendations** and **best practices** that should be exploited to policy makers. Though there is no Work Package or Task that is dedicated to developing policy recommendations, the exploitation plan will focus on identifying key policies that should be promoted and disseminated to key stakeholders.

2.4.2 Exploitation goals

Here the aim is to develop policy recommendations and support dialogue with policy makers at EU and national level, aiming to increase public investments for the cybersecurity protection of HDOs, and increase the potential that more HDOs will adopt the SPHINX toolkit.

A/A	Exploitation goal	Actions needed
1.	Dialogue with policy makers	Develop policy recommendations, best practices and lessons learnt based on the outcomes of different SPHINX Work Packages, especial the pilot activities. Conduct at least 10 meetings with policy makers (9 partner countries and at 1 at EU level) to inform them about the policy recommendations identified.

Table 6: Exploitation objectives for the SPHINX policy recommendations and best practices

2.5 Scientific and technical knowledge

2.5.1 Context

As already presented in “D1.2 Scientific and Innovation roadmap”, one of the goals of the SPHINX project is to devise a scientific and innovation roadmap that provides incremental steps necessary to achieve the SPHINX vision and guidelines to assist healthcare providers, industry and scientists to address externalities in order to improve innovation and competitiveness. The scientific roadmap, along with the community being built around it, focuses on giving good practice messages about technological issues in cybersecurity, and in particular to hospitals and the suppliers of medical devices, which have been selected by the SPHINX cybersecurity

community as the ones to be addressed first. The scientific roadmap focuses on the steps necessary for realising the most optimum use of cyber security techniques, toolkits and methodologies.

2.5.2 Exploitation goals

The SPHINX project will build a wide property of scientific knowledge. Academic partners should take this advantage and improve existing education on cybersecurity. The exploitation objectives are presented below:

A/A	Exploitation goal	Actions needed
1.	New and improved educational and scientific knowledge	3 educational infrastructures to be improved (1 per each University NTUA, HMU, VUB-LSTS)

Table 7: Exploitation objectives for the SPHINX scientific and technical knowledge

3 Summary of exploitation goals

Based on the project outcomes, a summary of the SPHINX exploitation goals is presented with the aim to **prepare the ground for its further sustainability**. For every exploitation goal, it has set a target to reach within the project duration. This information is summarised below:

Project overall			
A/A	Exploitation goal	SPHINX outcome	Target indicator
1	Maintain the pilot sites	SPHINX toolkit SPHINX components SPHINX pilot success stories	Pilot partners will present the pilot demonstration and its impact on the persons who are responsible for local and/or national funding (e.g. ministries) or private investment companies. We envisage having at least 6 meetings (2 per pilot partner)
2	Increase the potential to replicate the platform at external Health Delivery Organisations (HDO)	SPHINX toolkit SPHINX components SPHINX pilot success stories	The Pilot demonstration will be presented, along with the replication plans, to HDOs asking to express their interest and provide with feedback to the replication plans. We expect that at least 3 Health Delivery Organisations (1 per pilot country) will express their interest.
3	Verify the business potential of the platform in the health sector	SPHINX toolkit	Pilot demonstration, presentation of business cases and provision of insights for at least 3 companies (1 per pilot country)
4	Dialogue with policy makers	Policy recommendations and best practices	10 meetings with policy makers (9 partner countries and at 1 at EU level)
5	Wider adoption of the individual components	SPHINX components	9 industrial partners developing individual components (FINT, ICOM, PDMFC, KT, SIMAVI, TECHNALIA, EDGE, AIDEAS, TEC) should include that at their portfolio. Examine the possibility to implement business models for the components that have commercialisation potential.
6	New and improved educational and scientific knowledge	Scientific and technical knowledge	3 educational infrastructures to be improved (1 per each University NTUA, HMU, VUB-LSTS)

Table 8: Overall project specific goals and target indicators

Moving beyond the project end, when all project outcomes will be at their final version, the business plan and replication plans will be finalised, and the above targets will be achieved, the SPHINX consortium, both private and public partners, envisage to exploit the outcomes. In this respect, they have defined the exploitation goals,

for two years after the end of the project. The Tables below show for each partner type (private and public) the relevant information.

Partners from private companies (two IT Large Enterprises (SIMAVI, INTRA) and seven IT SMEs (FINT, KT, ViLabs, AiDEAS, PDMFC, EDGE, TEC))

A/A	Exploitation goal	SPHINX outcome	Indicator of success for the next 2 years after the end project
1.	SPHINX platform will be further developed to become a product ready to enter the market to assess and reduce cyber risks in Health Delivery organisations.	The SPHINX business plan will have strong evidence from the pilot demonstrations. It will be also introduced in the market at external Health Delivery Organisations which will express their interest to replicate it. In addition, the business plan will be verified by the industrial stakeholders. Having this information, partners from private companies agree to create a partnership to seek for funding or further investments	<p>Increase the customer base.</p> <p>Increase the revenues as a % of the total company profit on IT products/services.</p> <p>Expand the presence of the company into a new market.</p> <p>Sign a short- or long-term services contract agreement.</p>
2.	Develop new individual components that assess and reduce cyber risks in Health Delivery organisations.	Enhance company's portfolio with new solution/software components which impact has been identified through its demonstration in replicated real environments. This may stimulate future clients. E.g. replicate the SPHINX platform at external Health Delivery Organisations.	
3.	Develop new services (installation, training) at Health Delivery Organisations for the replication of 1. and 2.	Expand the knowledge gained from the pilot deployment and implementation, also the lessons learnt from how different problems have been met.	
4.	Create, improve and sustain the network of organisations in collaboration.	Improve the company's relationships within its network and expand new ones, by informing them	A number of new collaborative organisations added to the company's network.

		about SPHINX project and its use for their own needs. Disseminate the knowledge gained for expanding the company's offering, through its distribution channels.	New research and innovation projects generated with private and/or public funding.
5.	Employ new personnel through project participation	A number of new researchers have been employed, especially PhD students for practical training of their research application to replicated real environments.	A number of new personnel hired for the purpose of the project. Number of new employment positions sustained after the end of the project.
6.	Improve potential and skills of the existing personnel	Add value to the competencies of the existing staff through their involvement in the creation of new ideas and knowledge.	Number of existing personnel involved and specific skills acquired.

Partners from public organisations (three Universities (NTUA, HMU, VUB-LSTS), a Research Institute (TECNALIA), a Non-Profit Organisation (INCM), and three end users/Health Delivery Organisations (HDO) (DYPE5, POLARIS, HESE)

A/A	Exploitation goal	Justification	Indicator of success for the next 2 years after the end project
1	Maintain the pilot cases	The pilot partners having completed the demonstration, will have available the best practices that present the impact of its usage to minimise cyber security threads. Following the local and/or national funding (e.g. ministries) or private investment companies will act to receive the necessary funding and if needed (for example change of political party), additional meetings will take place.	Confirmation from local and/or national funding (e.g. ministries) or private investment companies to keep the SPHINX solution beyond the end of the project. Request for additional funding to sustain the technology (e.g. staff)
2	Increase the potential to replicate the platform at external Health Delivery Organisations	SPHINX vision is that HDO across Europe will adopt the platform. SPHINX will continue, beyond the end of the project, to promote the pilot demonstrations to HDOs (especially at the pilot countries, and at EU level) to attract their interest for adopting the SPHINX platform into their infrastructure.	The Pilot demonstration will continue to be promoted to HDOs motivating them to replicate it.

3	New and improved educational and scientific knowledge	The knowledge built through the project would support students and researchers to progress on novel IT solutions and services.	Additional scientific papers in this domain are expected to be produced. New courses are envisaged to be embedded in education.
4	Influence policies in the cybersecurity domain, at EU and national level	Impact generated through the pilot demonstration should be communicated with Policy Maker. The collaboration with relevant EU projects would increase the opportunities to reach a wider target audience.	SPHINX policy recommendations to be included within the upcoming policies on Cybersecurity.
5	New research collaborations	Apply SPHINX knowledge in new research projects in the future.	New research projects generated with private and/or public funding.

Table 9: List of potential Exploitation goals for private/public organisation partners for the next 2 years after the end of the project

Following the above definitions, the next table summarises for every exploitation outcome, the planned exploitation goals to reach until the end of the project and the corresponding goals to reach after the contractual project end, for the estimated period of two years.

A/A	Result/Asset	Exploitation goals	Indicator of success/metric	
			Until the end of the project	After the end of the project (2 years)
1	SPHINX platform	Stimulate the business potential of the platform in the health domain.	Define the IPRs. Sign contracts among partners to collectively exploit the results after the project ends, seek for funding or further investments.	Increase the customer base. Increase the revenues as a % of the total company profit on IT products/services.
2	SPHINX individual components	Expand the individual components, including them at business partners portfolio for direct business impact.	9 industrial partners developing individual components (FINT, ICOM, PDMFC, KT, SIMAVI, TECHNALIA, EDGE, AIDEAS, TEC) should include that at their portfolio.	Expand the presence of the company into a new market. Number of new collaborative organisations added in the company's network.
3	Replication guidelines	Increase potential to replicate the platform at external	The Pilot demonstration will be presented, along	

		Health Delivery Organisations	with the replication plans, to HDOs asking to express their interest and provide with feedback to the replication plan. We expect that at least 3 Health Delivery Organisations (1 per pilot country) will express their interest.	New research and innovation projects generated with private and/or public funding. Number of new employment positions sustained after the end of the project. The Pilot demonstration will continue to be promoted to HDOs motivating them to replicate it.
4	Pilot cases success stories	Maintain the pilot sites	Pilot partners will present the pilot demonstration and its impact on the persons who are responsible for local and/or national funding (e.g. ministries) or private investment companies. We envisage having at least 6 meetings (2 per pilot partner)	Confirmation from local and/or national funding (e.g. ministries) or private investment companies to keep the SPHINX solution beyond the end of the project. Request for additional funding to sustain the technology (e.g. staff)
5	SPHINX policy recommendations	Dialog with policy makers	10 meetings with policy makers (9 partner countries and at 1 at EU level)	SPHINX policy recommendations to be included within the upcoming policies on Cybersecurity.
6	Scientific and technical knowledge	New and improved education	3 educational infrastructures to be improved (1 per each University NTUA, HMU, VUB-LSTS)	Additional scientific papers in this domain are expected to be produced. New courses are envisaged to be embedded in education.

Table 10: Total Partners' exploitation goals and indicator of success/metrics before and after the end of the project

4 SPHINX business cases for exploitation

4.1 Context

The SPHINX business cases outline why the target market would be interested in the SPHINX toolkit, what would be the benefit the market will gain from the results, and propose through business models, how and who will create the bridge between the consortium and the target audience, aiming to bring the results to the market by the development of the SPHINX business plan. It is important to mention that the actions developed here are in line with the Innovation Management plan that was presented in WP1 and strong collaboration between the Innovation Management team and the Exploitation team is established.

4.2 Plan for exploiting the SPHINX toolkit

One of the main objectives of the SPHINX exploitation plan is to set up the environment for commercialising the main SPHINX toolkit. In this section the methodology for achieving these objectives is presented. The final outcome of the exploitation plan (on M36) will include the SPHINX business models and a business plan towards the commercialisation of the SPHINX toolkit.

The methodology that will be implemented to realise the SPHINX toolkit exploitation and commercialisation potential, consists of the following three phases:

- Business model exploration
- Business model experimentation
- Business model implementation

Business model exploration

Business model exploration phase is aimed at generating value propositions, inspired by the matching of the SPHINX outcomes to the unsatisfied market needs and gaps. These value propositions will be used as core components for the business models that will be developed in the next phase, namely “Business model experimentation”.

The aim of the Business model exploration phase is to identify the **market trends, gaps and opportunities**, and to come up with a strategy for **positioning the SPHINX toolkit and the SPHINX components in the market**. The Business model exploration phase will conduct an extensive market analysis while considering the SPHINX project outcomes in order to set the exploitation ground and thus challenge project partners to come up with **value propositions**. The main market targeted is the “healthcare cybersecurity”, as defined in the SPHINX Grant Agreement, and also as identified in the course of the project. For this market the state of play will be researched and presented. Relevant research projects will be reviewed, as well as organisations positioned in the market’s ecosystem. Key players will be identified and presented. Market dynamics will be illustrated and key performance indicators (KPIs) of the market will be discussed. The results of the Business model exploration phase will be presented in “**D8.9 Market analysis**” that will be delivered on M36. Work for this task has already started in order to feed the next phases of the exploitation plan. A preliminary full draft of the Market Analysis will be ready on M28 in order to feed the next phases of the current plan.

Business model experimentation

During the **Business model experimentation** phase, suggested value propositions will be identified and preliminary business models will be developed. A business modelling workshop will take place, where partners will discuss and define alternative value propositions resulting from the SPHINX outcomes. The value

propositions will be used to sketch the SPHINX business models. ViLabs (as task leader) will further work on these business models in order to validate their assumptions, expose their underlying logic, and document them. Then the consortium will come to select their “favourable” business models that will be presented in the next version of this deliverable on M36. In parallel, the business models will be presented to key stakeholders for feedback.

Business modelling workshop

The business modelling workshop aims to activate all partners in putting down their business ideas, considering their expertise. During the workshop, partners will receive a summary of guidelines about the aims of the workshop and under the guidance of ViLabs, they will identify the value propositions of the SPHINX outcomes (including the components that they are developing).

The SPHINX business models will be then generated using the Business Model Canvas method. A preliminary business model has already been identified as part of the Innovation Management task that is a summary of the Innovation Management activities that have been conducted until M24 of the project. This preliminary business model is presented in Section 4.2.4 of the current document.

Business model implementation

This next phase, namely the **Business model implementation** phase builds upon the selected business models towards a formal business operation, which may include further collaboration plans of project partners. This phase also includes the finalisation of the IPR strategy of the project that is part of Task 8.5 Knowledge Management and IPR Protection that will be delivered on M36.

The SPHINX exploitation plan will not only provide details on the exploitation paths of the SPHINX project partners, but also will refer to post-project actions that may be taken by these partners at will.

Below is the summary of important actions that the consortium needs to undertake in order to have a solid Exploitation, Sustainability and Exploitation plan for the SPHINX toolkit:

- Develop a **market analysis** and identify and describe the **customer segments**
- Create a **SWOT analysis**
- Identify, co-create, analyse and validate the **SPHINX business models**
- Describe the **Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs)** involved
- Based on the above develop the **SPHINX business plan** and identify the key actors (consortium partners) that would be willing to implement this business plan after the end of the project.

4.2.1 Market analysis

In order to better exploit SPHINX results, an analysis of the healthcare cybersecurity market needs to take place. The detailed market and customer segments analysis will be presented in “D8.9 Market analysis” that will be delivered on M36. This deliverable is the major outcome of “T8.2 Market Analysis and Identification of Customer Segments” and will focus on analysing the Healthcare cybersecurity market segment and will identify and present the key stakeholders / customers of the SPHINX platform. A very preliminary discussion on the market size is presented below while an overview of customer segments is provided in Section 3.1.2:

Healthcare cybersecurity market size

Increased connectivity to existing computer networks has exposed medical devices to new cybersecurity vulnerabilities [1]. Cyberattacks and data breaching are growing in the healthcare industry [2] for two fundamental reasons: it is a rich source of valuable data and its defences are weak. According to the Data Breach Barometer report, there were more than 40 million healthcare records exposed in 2019; almost tripled compared to 2018 that were 15 million.

According to a recent report [3] that was published in October 2020, the healthcare cybersecurity market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 19.8% from 2020 to reach 26.1 billion dollars by 2027.

Another report published in September 2020 by Fior Markets, mentions that the **global healthcare cyber security market** [4] is expected to grow from USD 9.78 billion in 2019 to USD 33.65 billion by 2027, at a CAGR of 19.3% during the forecast period 2020-2027.

The key factors driving the growth of the healthcare cybersecurity market [3] are:

- Increasing demand for advanced cybersecurity solutions and privacy
- increase in frequency and complexity of cyber threats
- emergence of disruptive digital technologies across the healthcare sector
- consistent technological developments

SPHINX toolkit **aims to introduce and promote a novel market field for security services, introducing new business cases and considerably expanding market opportunities** by attracting new entrants to the cyber security market. Especially SMEs and academia can leverage the SPHINX architecture by developing innovative cutting-edge Security Functions, which can be included in SPHINX toolkit, and rapidly introduced to the market, thus avoiding the delay and risk of hardware integration and prototyping.

SPHINX will provide the comprehensive solutions that the companies are looking for. Also, by catalysing the secure and anonymous exchange and analysis of security information through employing distributed ledger disruptive technologies and the creation of a decentralized decision support platform and analytical framework based on experimental blockchain techniques and common taxonomies, combining multidisciplinary insights from economics and engineering as well as behavioural and societal sciences, SPHINX will increase the predictive state of cybersecurity, enabling future preventive and responsive actions, targeted both to emerging IoT systems and devices, as well as traditional Internet connected computers.

Last, but not least, SPHINX will provide to the targeted market sector a set of recommendations addressed to relevant stakeholders (policy makers, regulators) as well as relevant market operators and/or insurance companies.

4.2.2 Customer segments

SPHINX business potential can directly impact two different stakeholder groups on the health and cybersecurity domain; the Health Provision Organisations (HPO) and the Industry (IoT and security). The Regulators/Policy Makers will be also engaged because they are the key stakeholders who influence the market.

Health Provision Organisations

The current state of the art in cybersecurity for the hospitals utilises a top-down approach, aiming to protect the system from cyber attacks but not to predict them. At the same time, there is a lack of tools for the modelling and prediction of cyber-attacks. For this reason, hospitals cannot efficiently monitor the network, and thus they are unable to protect patient data.

Naturally, the SPHINX platform will provide near-real time vulnerability assessment of HPO's operating IT Ecosystems. It will provide the means to HPOs to become aware and understand the cybersecurity risks (known or unknown threats and vulnerabilities) and to make informed decisions to choose only SPHINX certified devices, affecting their cyber-physical security and privacy. Naturally, the success of SPHINX platform is dependent also on the hospital staff's willingness to change the way they use the systems that will increase the data privacy and integrity.

The three project pilot sites (General Hospital of Volos (Greece), University Hospital of Larissa (Greece), Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (Portugal), and POLARIS Medical Clinic (Romania)) will evaluate the proposed

business cases that will easily motivate the hospital staff to align with the alerts they receive from the IT department about possible Cyber security threats.

Industry (IoT and security)

Industry at the IoT and security sector are an important market actor in the sector. They can be from different fields, such as:

- **Industry producing digital medical devices** (e.g., medication infusion systems, pacemakers) collecting personal health details are becoming more sophisticated and connected, allowing remote visualisation and the automatic incorporation of data in personal health records;
- **Industry producing digital wearables and IoT devices**, such as activity trackers, watches incorporating heart rate sensors, smart home sensors, albeit not rated as medical devices may produce data that is directly or indirectly relevant for purposes of assessing a patient's health and wellness status
- **Industry producing communication devices and enabling devices** such as tablets, phones which uphold info of patient, individual patient datagrams, patient photographs and variety of other sensitive info.
- **eHealth service providers**, software development industry producing the applications that analyse health data to visualise the tracking.
- **Cyber security service providers**, software development industry producing the services for cyber threads protection.
- **Cyber security practitioners**, experts in the security domain from software development industry.
- **Innovative start-ups, SMEs in the health domain** focusing on modern, digital critical infrastructures, and secure information systems

With revenue business-driven approach, they are supporting new business models to improve their positions in the markets. However, the industry lacks access at replicated real environments (e.g. hospitals) to evaluate the technology and forecast future needs, which constitutes a high market risk.

On the contrary, SPHINX will offer a platform and individual components that will be tested in three pilot sites and will also give industry the opportunity to test the medical equipment and get the detail compliant and certification report to assess if the device or service is vulnerable for misused or its attack surface is missing crucial security requirements and protects data privacy.

Complementary, the industry may provide valuable feedback to SPHINX on the proposed business plans to serve the targeted market needs.

Regulators/Policy Makers

The Regulators and Policy Makers in the cyber security for the Health sector are important lobbying actors because they can put pressure in decision-making procedures. On the one hand, they have to define long term regulations to ensure stability in the market while on the other hand, it is important that the business models are aligned with relevant regulations.

The most crucial information for Regulators and Policy Makers is how the market reacts from reliable simulations. The SPHINX project, through the application of technology in real environments, will be able to provide them with technical and financial information along with the social impact.

SPHINX will also investigate improvements and alternatives to current institutional and governance frameworks in order to improve cybersecurity awareness and stimulate the usage of the proposed solution aiming to empower patient data privacy.

4.2.3 SWOT analysis

In the Innovation Management plan that is presented in “D1.2 Scientific and Innovation Management” a SWOT analysis was presented as a result from the SPHINX partners contribution. While the ideas of the partners tangled to the specific tool that they are developing there are a number of common characteristics that are shared. This SWOT analysis will become the basis for our updated SWOT that is presented in Table X below.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>SPHINX toolkit is vendor independent and protocol agnostic</p> <p>SPHINX can be tailored to the needs of the customers (Health Provision Organisations)</p> <p>SPHINX toolkit is user friendly (end-user understanding through interactive dashboards)</p> <p>SPHINX toolkit is interoperable with third party tools and services</p> <p>SPHINX toolkit can automate tasks and increase performance</p>	<p>SPHINX toolkit is composed of several components developed by different partners / different IPRs involved</p> <p>Increased maintenance and developing costs</p> <p>Extensive simulation of real systems will increase the solution’s complexity</p>
Opportunities	Threats
<p>Smart healthcare market expected to skyrocket in an increasingly complex cyber security environment</p> <p>Rising patient or user (e.g. doctor) concern on cyber security</p> <p>Open-source tools are being used for the development of the different components</p> <p>SPHINX toolkit can be applied in different markets and application domains</p> <p>Market need for low-cost usable security solutions</p>	<p>The competition is big and market operators and companies tend to rely on “brand name” software suppliers</p> <p>The lack of interoperability and poor standardisation in medical equipment/IoT/smart health infrastructure industry, raising barriers for wider market penetration</p> <p>Interoperability/integration failures both amongst SPHINX components and also with the third-party solutions</p>

Table 11: Preliminary SPHINX SWOT analysis

This is a preliminary version of the SPHINX SWOT analysis. It will be updated by all consortium partners during the business modelling workshop that will be conducted between month 30 and month 32 of the project. During that period the first results of the pilots will be already available, the components will be ready, and it will be more clear on what the different SWOT elements of SPHINX are.

4.2.4 SPHINX business models

By the end of month 34, SPHINX will have already develop and validate the business models for the SPHINX toolkit. The business models will describe how an entity can create, deliver and capture value taking advantage of the SPHINX toolkit. A preliminary business model has been drafted by the Innovation Management team taking advantage of partner’s contributions to the Innovation Management surveys that have been distributed. This business model that is presented in Figure 3 will act as a basis for the final business models that will be developed. The SPHINX business models that will be developed will be the result of:

- A thorough examination of the available business models/strategies for open-source software and their multiple variations.
- A business modelling workshop that will be conducted in SPHINX where all consortium partners will be present.
- The main results of the SPHINX toolkit evaluation that will be derived from WP7.
- The results of a Market Analysis that will be conducted in “D7.1 Market Analysis”.
- A thorough feedback that we will aim to receive from experts in the field where we will have the opportunity to pitch the SPHINX business model. The core SPHINX business model will be presented and validated during an event that will be organised by the SPHINX consortium.

Based on the identified business models the SPHINX business and exploitation plan will be developed. The preliminary SPHINX business model is presented below utilising the Business Model Canvas methodology [5]:

Figure 3: SPHINX preliminary business model

Customers served: Starting from the “Customers” for whom we are delivering the value (and would be willing to pay for the SPHINX product), the consortium identified three types of customers: a) Public and private healthcare organisations (hospitals, clinics and care centres), b) Insurance companies and c) Certification authorities. A more detailed analysis of the needs of the SPHINX customers will be presented in “D8.9 Market analysis”.

What is SPHINX offering to its customers (value): Moving to the “Value propositions” segment which is the value that we are delivering to our customers and the needs that we are satisfying, SPHINX provides a) an automated and intelligent Cybersecurity protection mechanism for the healthcare sector (protection against

Cybersecurity attacks, maintaining patients' data, help healthcare workers to perform their work), b) the ability to certify devices, systems, components and applications.

What relationships is SPHINX establishing with its customers (customer relationships): The customer relationships as these are defined by the SPHINX consortium are: a) Long-term, meaning that SPHINX will interact with the customers on a recurring basis, b) Personal assistance meaning that the customer can communicate with SPHINX after a purchase is complete (onsite, through email, call centres etc.), c) training sessions, workshops and pitch events that will be organised for the customers by SPHINX.

What are the resources that underpin this business model: Every business model requires Key Resources to run. In SPHINX the consortium identified: a) IT infrastructure, b) Human resources for research, development and support, c) Human resources for marketing purposes.

Which activities are needed in this business model (key activities): The most important things SPHINX must do to make its business model work are: a) Further development and integration, b) continuous testing and validation, c) marketing and sales.

Which partners leverage this business model: The partnerships and the network that will make the business model work are the following: a) SPHINX consortium (mainly the developers of the components and the business experts willing to take up the results), b) Public and private healthcare organisations (Hospitals, clinics, care centres), c) Insurance companies, d) Medical / healthcare device providers, e) Certification authorities.

Which channels are being used: SPHINX communicates with and reaches the customers to deliver the value proposition with the following ways: a) Online channels (website, social media), b) Sales partners/distributors, c) Healthcare authorities, d) certification authorities.

Which key resources / activities are most expensive (cost structure): The costs that are important to operate the SPHINX business model are the following: a) Development and integration costs, b) Marketing and Sales costs, c) Training costs, d) Infrastructure and cloud service costs.

How would the customers prefer to pay for SPHINX (revenue streams): The revenue streams that represent the way SPHINX will generate cash from the customers are the following: a) Subscription fees, b) Direct sales (one-time payment), c) Licensing fees (scalability), d) Maintenance and support fees, e) Training and consulting fees.

In this section we presented a preliminary version of the SPHINX Business model, using the Business Model Canvas methodology. A more detailed version will be outlined in in "D8.10: Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v3" on M36.

4.2.5 IPRs of the SPHINX toolkit

Management of intellectual property rights plays an important role in all Horizon 2020 research projects. In SPHINX, where nine partners are leading the development of twenty different components, it is becoming obvious that the way partners will handle the IPRs of their components will play critical role to the development of a potential business plan. For that reason, a specific task (T8.5 Knowledge Management and IPR Protection) dedicated to the IPR management is foreseen. The outcomes of this task will be reported in "D8.11 SPHINX IPR Plan & IPR Management v2" on M36. It is critical that between M30 and M34 this task will define the IPRs of how the different SPHINX components will be exploited. The exploitation workshop that is foreseen will also include a dedicated session on the management of IPRs and then partners will be asked to state their preferences on which IPR strategy is foreseen for their component in the exploitation strategy of SPHINX.

4.3 Plan for exploiting the SPHINX components

The process of identifying potential business models for the individual components has already started in D1.2 where the different SPHINX innovation management phases (Exploration phase, Definition phase and Building a Business Case phase) assisted partners in eliciting insights for building potential business cases for their individual components. Towards this direction, webinars are foreseen where the exploitation and the innovation management team will guide partners on identifying the value of their components. For the components that do have clear commercialisation potential, technical partners with the assistance of the exploitation team will build appropriate business models. The process of building a business case from individual components is the following:

1. Gather feedback from “D1.2 Scientific and Innovation Roadmap” and record the key points.
2. Exploitation options will be discussed during the “Workshop on guiding the consortium on exploitation prospects” that will be held on M25 of the project.
3. Bilateral discussions between the exploitation and innovation management team and the nine technical partners leading the development of the components.
4. The exploitation team will organise a webinar targeted to technical and scientific partners where the process of building a business case is explained.
5. Distribute the SPHINX exploitation questionnaire.
6. Collect the SPHINX questionnaires and draft the first results from the questionnaires.
7. For the partners interested in commercialising their outcomes, work on identifying appropriate business models.
8. Draft the results in “D8.10 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v3” on M36.

5 Sustainability plan

5.1 Context

SPHINX project will deliver an IT solution that will be tested and demonstrated in three different countries (Romania, Portugal and Greece) aiming to contribute to the expected impacts set out in the H2020 work programme '**Toolkit for assessing and reducing cyber risks in hospitals and care centres to protect privacy/data/infrastructures**'.

SPHINX will also develop the sustainability plan to maximise the impact and secure that the project results will remain active and even further expanded, beyond the contractual project end. The sustainability plan aim is four-fold:

- **Pilot organisations maintain the SPHINX platform.** During the project progress, the four project pilot sites (General Hospital of Volos (Greece), University Hospital of Larissa (Greece), Hospital do Espírito Santo de Évora (Portugal), and POLARIS Medical Clinic (Romania)) will demonstrate the SPHINX platform in a replicated real environment but with limited data. After the completion of the project, the platform TRL will be increased but not ready to enter the market with real patient data. Therefore, a partnership will be created that will be comprised of some SPHINX partners to work in order to find further funding (e.g. other funding opportunities) and proceed to continue the platform development while the pilots will be able to continue testing the SPHINX platform.
- **New Health Provision Organisations replicate the SPHINX platform.** The SPHINX platform is designed in a scalable manner in order to be used by different IT infrastructures that hospitals across Europe may have. In addition, the steps that project pilots will follow to deploy the platform will be generated into replication plans that any Health Provision Organisation will be able to follow to deploy SPHINX platform.
- **Verify the business potential of the SPHINX platform.** The business plan will be developed during the project to facilitate the business exploitation of the platform which will be evaluated by the stakeholders from the targeted market, to conclude on a mature plan of high potential. Partners will agree on a partnership to proceed and investigate to further funding, to develop this RIA result into a product ready to enter the market. The detailed plan for developing the business plan is presented in Section 4.2).
- **Proceed with the further usage of the other exploitable outcomes.** Industrial partners envisage to include the individual components at their portfolios. The partners from the public sector will expand the project results which apply in their activities (pilot cases success stories, replication guidelines, policy recommendations, scientific and technical knowledge).

Figure 4: SPHINX sustainability plan approach

5.2 Methodology

The SPHINX consortium will implement the project with the vision to prepare the ground and reach the sustainability goals. The partner of common organisation types will work collaboratively towards the different goals:

Pilot organisations maintain the SPHINX platform: The IT private organisations will work collaboratively to develop the SPHINX platform that will deliver to the end-user partners. They will test the platform in their replicated real environments, against targeted risks and threats including combined cyber and physical attacks. In parallel, end-user partners will also monitor and control the cyber security and privacy risks, threats and incidents in terms of reliability of the real-time risk assessment, effectiveness in the prevention and mitigation of typical cyber security and privacy risks and user satisfaction. In this way, end-user organisations will validate the platform and communicate the findings of the pilot operation of the services with the IT private organisation to improve the SPHINX platform initial deployment to prepare an outlook for its large-scale usability.

As a result, by the end of the project the SPHINX platform will be tested in replicated real environment, but it will not be ready to be installed and run at hospitals with real data. Further research and development should be carried out to increase its TRL level. In this respect, during the project progress partners will agree on a partnership that will act to find the funding to continue the research work and pilot demonstration.

The process of working towards maintaining the SPHINX platform to pilot organisations is the following:

1. Implement the pilot activities
2. Validate the platform and communicate the findings
3. The exploitation team will organise a webinar targeted to pilot partners where the exploitation objectives are presented together with a plan on how to achieve them
4. Record the feedback from the webinar
5. Pilot partners present the pilot demonstrations and its impact on the persons who are responsible for local and/or national funding (e.g. ministries) or private investment companies
6. Report all actions in “D8.10 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v3” on M36

New Health Provision Organisations replicate the SPHINX platform: During the pilot preparation and deployment phase, the end-user organisations will develop the guidelines on how to replicate the hospital’s ICT setup involving workstations, software applications, medical databases and connected medical devices, in order to adopt the SPHINX platform. As a next step, end-user organisations will take actions to communicate the successful deployment of the platform, the impact and the replication guidelines, with their existing

network of Health Provision Organisations to attract their interest and motivate them to adopt later the mature SPHINX platform to their premises, when it will be a ready product.

The process of working towards the replication of the platform to other HDOs is the following:

1. Develop replication guidelines
2. Share the replication guidelines to other HDOs (at least 3)
3. Receive feedback and expression of interests from potential “customers”
4. “D8.10 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v3” on M36

Verify the business potential of the SPHINX platform: IT industry and SME partners will co-design with the exploitation manager the SPHINX business models. To increase the business potential, they will take actions to present the business models at the targeted audience in order to receive feedback and verify that SPHINX proposed approach meets their needs. In addition, SPHINX consortium is aiming to get benefit of the strong demonstrations that will be implemented within the project timeframe, and present to the potential market the benefits of the SPHINX platform and its components in replicated real environment conditions. The process of working towards building the SPHINX business models is presented in Section 4.2.

Further usage of the other exploitable outcomes: A rich property of scientific knowledge will be produced during the project implementation through the mature research that experienced partners will carry out in this innovative discipline of cyber security in the health sector. Partners from Universities and research centres will take the necessary actions to expand this knowledge at new researchers and progress on this field. In addition, evidenced based policy recommendations will be outlined from the pilot demonstrations. Partners from public authorities will communicate such information at EU and national level.

The process of working towards the further use of the exploitable outcomes is the following:

1. Identify the key policy recommendations from the project (via questionnaire that will be distributed to all partners)
2. Identify relevant events (both national and EU level) that these policy recommendations could be presented
3. Organise and publish results in international journals, conferences, and workshops to inform the scientific community about SPHINX, its goals, activities and results and to gather valuable information on related issues.
4. Identify the possibility to improve educational infrastructures (1 per each University NTUA, HMU, VUB-LSTS)
5. Report the actions in “D8.10 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v3” on M36

6 Individual exploitation plans

Partners' preliminary individual exploitation plans have been reported in two SPHINX deliverables so far:

- a) in "D8.4 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v1" (M12) where partners had the opportunity to describe in detail their profile, their exploitation goals, their exploitable project results and the value created for their organization through their participation in SPHINX project.
- b) In "D1.2: Scientific and Innovation roadmap" (M23) where partners had the opportunity to briefly describe their intentions with regards to the exploitation of the project's results.

The final version of the individual exploitation plan of the different partners will be presented in "D8.10 Exploitation, Sustainability & Business Plans v3" on M36. Towards defining the partners' exploitation strategies, the following actions are considered:

- a) The Exploitation team together with the Innovation Management team will organise a workshop (M25) to familiarize the partnership with exploitation and sustainability terms and guide them on developing their strategy to exploit the SPHINX outcomes both at individual level and at the level of the consortium as a whole.
- b) ViLabs will prepare a questionnaire asking project partners to provide a description about their exploitation plans, both at individual level (outputs to be exploited by them) and at project's level (evaluation of different scenarios, namely possible joint ventures and licensing). The questionnaire will be reviewed by partners and will be distributed to the consortium after the exploitation workshop (between M30 and M34).
- c) ViLabs will analyse the results obtained from the questionnaires and will integrate them in D8.10.

Questionnaire's contents and time-line

The questionnaire will be distributed on M30 and a first draft version is included in Annex I. The questionnaire is composed of the following four parts:

Introduction

- Rationale of the questionnaire, explaining the need to provide the consortium with a better understanding of how each organisation foresees the exploitation and sustainability of SPHINX.
- Direct request of all partners' contributions, asking them to write a few descriptive lines per question detailing their information, ideas and opinions about the exploitation plans.
- Explanation of key concepts regarding the concepts of "exploitation plan" and "sustainability".

Basic Data Collection

- Identification of the person answering the questionnaire to have an overview of each partner's contributor's (full name, organisation, position email address, Skype ID if applicable).

Part 1: Questions about "Exploitation plan at each organisation's level"

- Questions directed to receive input about each partner individual exploitation plan aiming to clarify which were the expected outcomes from SPHINX when they joined the project, which are the outcomes being exploited at the moment and how they will be exploited after the project. A question about the Intellectual Property Rights is also included.

Part 2: Questions about "Exploitation plan at SPHINX consortium level"

- Questions directed at receiving input about each partner's vision on what exploitation measures should be carried out by the consortium as a whole to better use the project results and ensure the sustainability of SPHINX solution and its components beyond the project's lifecycle, and on the project's impact on science, technology and society.

The questionnaire is further envisaged to evaluate the project's exploitation strategies and SPHINX business models in more detail, thus providing an opportunity to gather partners' ideas on how to use the project results and products at the local, regional, national, European and/or international levels. Based on the results of this questionnaire ViLabs (as a leader of the exploitation activities) will be able to clearly identify, analyse and describe: 1) the SPHINX partners' individual exploitation plans; 2) the SPHINX consortium joint exploitation plan.

7 Plan of exploitation activities for Year 3

In this section we present a summary and a timeline with all the activities that need to be carried out during the third year of the project in order to maximize the exploitation, sustainability and business potential of the key SPHINX project outcomes. In order to successfully implement the exploitation and sustainability plan that was presented in the previous sections the following actions will be conducted:

A/A	Exploitation activity	Who?	When?	KPIs
1	Workshop on guiding the consortium on exploitation prospects. The objective is to familiarise the partnership with exploitation and sustainability terms and guide them on developing their strategy to exploit the SPHINX outcomes both at individual level and at the level of the consortium as a whole.	All consortium partners	M25	A list with all the exploitation actions that each partner is willing to undertake during the last year of the project. Monitor these actions.
1	Market analysis finalization	Exploitation team with minor assistance of technical partners	Between M25-M29	Draft version of the Market analysis document ready
2	Exploitation workshop to work on the SPHINX business models, SPHINX SWOT analysis and SPHINX IPRs	All consortium partners	Between M30-M32	Consortium should a) Select the SPHINX business models b) decide on the IPRs involved c) agree on the SPHINX SWOT analysis
3	Webinar targeted to technical and scientific partners where the process of building a business case is explained	Technical partners and the Exploitation team	Between M27-M28	9 technical partners include their components that at their portfolio 1-2 business models developed.
4	Webinar targeted to pilot partners where the exploitation objectives are presented together with a plan on how to achieve them	Pilot partners and the Exploitation team	Between M30-M32	Business models validated by SPHINX pilots and guidelines
5	Pilot partners present the pilot demonstrations and its impact on the persons who are responsible for local and/or national funding (e.g.	Pilot partners	Between M32-M34	At least three demonstrations to key stakeholders (1 per pilot)

	ministries) or private investment companies			
6	Organise a mini workshop to validate the SPHINX business models with external experts	Companies in the cybersecurity domain	Between M32-M34	Pilot demonstration, presentation of business cases and provision of insights from at least 3 companies
7	Distribute to all partners the exploitation questionnaire	All consortium partners	M33	All consortium partners complete the exploitation questionnaire
8	Develop replication guidelines	Pilot partners with the assistance of the Exploitation team	M33	Guidelines shared to at least other 3 HDOs. Feedback received.
9	Identify key policy recommendations and best practices	All partners	M34	Policy recommendations identified and validated by the consortium
10	Disseminate and Exploit the policy recommendations	All partners	M35-M36	Implement at least 10 (9 local and 1 EU) dissemination activities
11	Present the SPHINX toolkit to the three pilot workshops that WP7 is organising together with WP8: 1. Cybersecurity Awareness in Healthcare Employees, Location: Greece; 2. The SPHINX Universal Toolkit for Healthcare Organisations, Location: Portugal; 3. The Impact of SPHINX in Healthcare Organisations: Pilot Results, Location: Romania.	Staff of the Health Delivery Organisations of the SPHINX pilot sites / Consortium partners	4 th quarter of 2020 (December 2020), 3 rd quarter of 2021, 4 th quarter of 2021.	At least 50 participants in each workshop should be informed about the SPHINX toolkit.

Table 12: Plan of Year 3 exploitation activities

8 Conclusions

This document presents the second updated version of the SPHINX exploitation and sustainability plan. The document begins with a presentation of the SPHINX main exploitable outcomes (Section 2) and provides a summary of the exploitation goals for these outcomes (3). The document continues with an analysis of the plan for identifying the SPHINX business models and for presenting the SPHINX business plan (Section 4) while the plan for sustaining the results of the project is presented in Section 5. In addition to the initial individual exploitation plans that have already been presented in the previous version of this deliverable and this document presents the exploitation questionnaire that will be distributed to partners for gathering feedback with regards to their individual exploitation plans (Section 6). Finally, the document concludes with a summary of all the Exploitation Activities (Section 7) that will be carried out during the final year of the project in order to make sure that all the project outcomes will be disseminated, communicated and exploited appropriately to the right target audience.

The final SPHINX exploitation plan (D8.10) will present a consolidated view of the SPHINX exploitation options, as these will be defined by the consortium, and will further define the needed actions for the commercialisation of the SPHINX outcomes, including:

- the individual exploitation plans of each SPHINX partner,
- the co-operative exploitation plans of the SPHINX consortium, and
- a plan for follow-up commercial exploitation activities, to be pursued by interested partners.

9 References

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- [4] Fior Markets (2020). Healthcare Cyber Security Market by Type Of Threat (Distributed Denial Of Service, Malware & Spyware, Ransomware, Phishing, Spear-Phishing), Deployment (Cloud-Based, On-Premises), Security Measure (Network Security, Application Security, Device Security), Region, Global Industry Analysis, Market Size, Share, Growth, Trends, and Forecast 2020 to 2027. Available at: <https://www.fiormarkets.com/report/healthcare-cyber-security-market-by-type-of-threat-418898.html>.
- [5] Strategyzer (2020), The Business Model Canvas. Available at: <https://www.strategyzer.com/canvas/business-model-canvas>

Appendix I: SPHINX exploitation questionnaire

Dear colleague,

Please spend a few minutes answering this questionnaire.

This questionnaire is SPHINX consortium's tool to collect information concerning all partners' strategy to exploit the SPHINX project outcomes both at individual level and at the level of the consortium as a whole. It will also serve the consortium to analyse your ideas and opinions about the exploitation prospects of the SPHINX project.

Your answers will be analysed, synthesized and included in deliverable D8.10 "Exploitation, Sustainability and Business Plans v2". This RAPP Project Exploitation plan is requested by the European Commission to assess the viability of the project after its completion.

Thank you for being analytical and specific while providing all thoughts and ideas.

Key concepts:

EXPLOITATION PLANS

The European Commission pays great attention to the project's measures to maximize the impact of the results on science, technology and society. Precisely, ensuring that project outcomes are widely "disseminated" beyond the partners' audience as well as effectively "exploited" guarantees the utility of the results after the project and, therefore, it is the source of accountability of projects funded by taxpayers' money.

To develop an Exploitation Plan is a systematic requirement for EU-funded projects, which should detail how the individual project partners and the consortium as a whole intend to make use of the research results, with the aim of taking advantage of all activities in the project. While some partners will only foresee an improvement of their expertise, or level of publications; others might envision concrete exploitation perspectives based on more or less formalised business models. **Part 1** of the present questionnaire focuses on exploitation plans at each partner's level. **Part 2** is devoted to gather ideas and opinions from partners about how the global exploitation plan should be implemented by the consortium.

SUSTAINABILITY

The European Commission envisages the funding of research projects as a previous step in the development of a more ambitious path by part of or all consortium partners, in such a way that research outcomes lead to a pre-commercial or commercial phase where no EU funding is necessary, and where consortium partners have found a way, often through business models, to ensure continuity of the project efforts beyond the overall project lifecycle.

Precisely, as far as consortium partners are co-investing in the project's research, they are expected to have similar interests to exploit project outcomes, thus ensuring the sustainability of their project. A credible "sustainability plan" is one of the most valuable outputs of the project.

Please indicate in the below table the name(s) of the representative(s) of your organisation providing answers to this questionnaire. Several representatives from your organisation may usefully fill in this questionnaire in order to provide the consortium with a better understanding of the way your organisation foresees the exploitation and sustainability of the project

	Contributor 1	Contributor 2	Contributor 3
Full name			
Organization			
Position			
Email address			

Part 1: Exploitation plans at your organisation's level

Q1. What did your organization achieve by getting involved in the SPHINX project? (Increase of your expertise in x domain, knowledge acquisition, network enhancement, commercial opportunities, scientific/ technological advances, etc.)

Q2. Which of the SPHINX outcomes is your organisation planning to exploit?

Q3. How does your organisation plan to exploit the SPHINX outcomes after the project?

Part 2: "Towards the sustainability of the RAPP Joint Initiative"

Q4. If your organisation was to be involved in a joint initiative for the exploitation of the SPHINX project, which of the above business models would better fit its needs? Please provide your comments, remarks, on the selected business models:

Q5. What, in your opinion, are the key SPHINX developments and measures necessary to successfully apply the selected business model?

Q6. What, in your opinion, are the main obstacles faced by the RAPP partnership towards the implementation of the business models?

Q7. Do you have any recommendations regarding the proposed RAPP business models? Do you have other exploitation ideas that are not satisfied by the proposed business models?

Many thanks for finishing this survey - your feedback is sincerely appreciated!

